

Neurofibroma of Posterior Cervical Space: A Case ReportSudesh Kumar¹, Ankit Chaudhary²¹Assistant Professor, MD Radio-diagnosis, Dr RKGMC Hamirpur, Himachal Pradesh²Programme Officer, MD Community Medicine, Regional Hospital Una, Himachal Pradesh

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Abstract:

The tumours of posterior cervical space in posterior triangle of neck region are rare. Whereas benign tumours rarely occur in posterior cervical space, the metastatic squamous cell carcinoma is the most common lesion of posterior cervical space. The lesions occurring in this space can be characterized on the basis of features exhibited on different radiological diagnostic modalities, however final diagnosis can be made only on histopathological examination. Here CT findings of neurofibroma of posterior cervical space are reported which presented as a swelling in lateral aspect of neck. The contrast enhancement was comparable to the skeletal muscle and the lesion lacked fat density areas, necrotic areas and calcification. The mass had displaced the major neck vessels anteromedially.

Keywords: Posterior Cervical Space, Neurofibroma.

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Introduction

The posterior cervical space is a space in infrahyoid compartment of neck extending from skull base superiorly to the clavicle inferiorly. The sternocleidomastoid muscle forms the anterior margin and trapezius muscle forms the posterior margin of posterior cervical space. The space usually houses fat, spinal accessory nerve, brachial plexus, dorsal scapular nerve and lymph nodes. [1,2] The most common lesion of posterior cervical space is metastatic squamous cell carcinoma. [2] Although there is 25-45 % incidence of neurogenic tumours in head and neck region [3], yet the neurofibromas rarely occur in head and neck region.[10]

The neurofibroma has no gender predilection and occurs more commonly in the age group of 20-40 years[10]. We report a rare case of neurofibroma of posterior cervical space appearing as fusiform shaped soft tissue mass lesion in posterior cervical region.

Case Presentation and Imaging

A 41 years old male presented with single progressively increasing swelling in neck region for the past 06-08 months. There was no history of difficulty in swallowing/drinking, hoarseness of voice, fever, associated pain or weight loss. On

examination, there was a lump on left side of neck with smooth contour and was firm on palpation and the overlying skin appeared normal. No evidence of enlarged cervical lymph nodes was observed. The cranial nerves examination seemed normal. The contrast enhanced Computerized Tomography (CT) Neck was performed on single slice CT scan and 5 mm sections were obtained (Image 1 and 2). There was well defined oval shaped soft tissue mass lesion 06 cm (anteroposterior), 05 cm (transverse) cm and 07 cm (cranio-caudal) in extent located in left posterior cervical space and enhancement was comparable to the skeletal muscle. No evidence of any fat density areas, necrotic areas, calcification was recorded. The mass had displaced the common carotid artery and internal jugular vein anteromedially. No adjacent structure was infiltrated by the lesion. This mass was abutting the transverse process of vertebra posteriorly. The radiological impression of nerve sheath tumour of posterior cervical space was made based on localization and CT characteristics. The patient was operated and the tumour was excised completely. Grossly the mass was grey white to grey brown on appearance; while on histopathological examination, the spindle cells consistent with neurofibroma were documented.

Image 1: There is presence of well-defined homogeneously enhancing mass lesion in left posterior cervical space with maintained fat planes; with sternocleidomastoid muscle anteriorly and levator scapula muscle posteriorly displacing carotid vessels and internal jugular vein anteromedially.

Image 2: Sagittal image showing oval shaped mass lesion in posterior cervical space between sternocleidomastoid and trapezius muscle.

Discussion

The metastatic squamous cell carcinoma is the most common lesion and lipoma is the most common benign lesion in posterior cervical space. [2] The neurofibromas can occur in carotid space where it may arise from vagus nerve or sympathetic chain; and in posterior cervical space where it may arise from spinal accessory nerve or brachial plexus. The neurofibromas are well defined lesions and have fusiform shape. [4] The tumours presenting in the posterior cervical space tend to displace the common carotid artery and internal jugular vein anteriorly which was in corroboration with our observations. The cervical sympathetic trunk lies in posteromedial relation to the carotid sheath and any mass arising from it will cause anterolateral displacement of internal carotid artery. [5] The other important differential is vagal schwannoma or

paraganglioma. Since, the vagus nerve courses in between the internal carotid artery or common carotid artery and internal jugular vein, therefore any mass arising from vagus nerve will separate internal carotid artery and jugular vein. [5,7,8,9,10]

Peripheral nerve sheath tumors are of two types namely, neurofibroma and schwannoma. Schwannoma arise from Schwann cells, grows eccentrically and are characterized by verocay bodies seen microscopically. The neurofibroma arise from perineural fibroblast and is intertwined with in the fascicles of nerve. [6,10] Schwannomas are encapsulated tumours whereas neurofibromas are circumscribed and are not encapsulated. [3,6] The nerve sheath tumours have smooth margins and fusiform shape and are iso-to-hypodense on non-contrast CT and are hypo vascular in nature. Schwannoma shows heterogenous enhancement on

post-contrast images due to presence of cystic, necrotic areas and due to hypocellularity which are less common in neurofibroma. [10] Apart from nerve sheath tumours the other pathologies that can occur in posterior cervical space are enlarged lymph nodes, lymphoma or lymphangioma. The other important lesions which have to be kept in mind while evaluation of head and neck masses are carotid body tumour and vagal paraganglioma. The carotid body tumour causes splaying of external and internal carotid arteries whereas the vagal paraganglioma displace carotid vessels anteriorly and internal jugular vein posteriorly. [7] The paragangliomas are easy to detect as they show strong enhancement on contrast study. [7,11]

Conclusion

The tumours of posterior cervical space are rare and understanding of anatomy and differential diagnosis is very important in diagnosis. Though the CT scan can help us in localizing and differentiating the lesion, however definitive confirmation can be made only on histopathological examination. The present case of neurofibroma of posterior cervical space showed poor to mild homogenous post-contrast enhancement displacing the common carotid artery and internal jugular vein anteriorly. The Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is better in evaluating these masses because of better soft tissue detailing, resolution and other MR characteristics.

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